

D5.7 FINAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT REPORT

Project Full Title	RDA Europe 4.0 – The European plug-in to the global Research Data Alliance
Project Acronym	RDA Europe 4.0
Project Number	777388
Start Date of Project	01.03.2018
Duration of Project	31 Months
Project Website	www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe
Deliverable Title	Final Impact Assessment Report
Deliverable No.	D5.7
Author(s)	M. Willems (TRUST-IT), S. Pittonet (TRUST-IT), L. Colucci (TRUST-IT), S. Garavelli (TRUST-IT)
Abstract	This is the final of two reports that tracks the impact assessment achieved by the RDA Europe 4.0 project..

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

The work described in this document has been conducted within the project RDA Europe 4.0. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 (H2020) research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no 777388. This document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Document Information

Deliverable Title	Impact assessment report
Deliverable No.	D5.7
Contractual Delivery Date	30/09/2020
Actual Delivery Date	
Author(s)	Marieke Willems, Sara Pittonet, Luigi Colucci, Sara Garavelli (TRUST-IT)
Editor(s)	
Contributor(s)	Ryan O'Connor (UEDIN), Ilaria Fava (UGOE), Timea Biro (DRI)
Reviewer(s)	Hilary Hanahoe (RDA F), Ingrid Dillo (DANS)
Work Package Number & Title	WP5 - Communication, Marketing, Impact & Sustainability
Work Package Leader	TRUST-IT
Work Package Participants	UGOE, RIA, UEDIN

Versioning and Revision History

Versio n	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	22/07/2020	Marieke Willems (TRUST-IT)	ToC
0.2	01/09/2020	Marieke Willems (TRUST-IT)	Chapter 1, 2, 3 and 4
0.3	07/09/2020	Ryan O'Connor (UEDIN)	Contributions chapter 4
0.4	14/09/2020	Ilaria Fava (UGOE)	Contributions chapter 2, 3 and 4
0.5	15/09/2020	Timea Biro (DRI)	Contributions chapter 2, 3 and 4
0.6	15/10/2020	Sara Pittonet & Luigi Colucci (TRUST-IT)	Contributions chapter 2 and 3
0.7	20/10/2020	Marieke Willems (TRUST-IT)	Overall contributions
0.8	25/10/2020	Sara Garavelli (TRUST-IT)	Internal review & feedback

0.9	3/11/2020	Ingrid Dillo (DANS), Hilary Hanahoe (RDA F)	Internal review
1.0	5/11/2020	Marieke Willems, Sara Garavelli, Sara Pittonet (TRUST-IT), Timea Biro (DRI)	Comments addressed and final version

Disclaimer

RDA Europe 4 (777388) is a Coordination & Support Action co-funded by the European Commission under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Horizon 2020 (H2020).

This document contains information on RDA Europe (Research Data Alliance Europe 4.0) core activities. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation, and publication date.

The document has been produced with the funding of the European Commission. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the RDA Europe Consortium, and it cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission. The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 28 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (http://europa.eu/index_en.htm).

Copyright notice: This work is licensed under the Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0 licence. To view a copy of this licence, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>.

The content of the document herein is the sole responsibility of the publishers and it does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services. The RDA Europe 4 Consortium does not guarantee that any information contained herein is error-free, or up to date. THE RDA Europe 4.0 CONSORTIUM MAKES NO WARRANTIES, EXPRESS, IMPLIED, OR STATUTORY, BY PUBLISHING THIS DOCUMENT.

Glossary

Abbreviation	Definition
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
CCCA	Climate Change Centre Austria
CESSDA	Consortium European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	European Research Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technology
CODATA	Committee on Data for Science and Technology
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC EB	European Open Science Cloud Executive Board
ESFRI	European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
ICDI	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure
IAC	Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology
IG	Interest Group
ICSU	International Council for Science
INRA	French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment
MSP	Multi-Stakeholders Platform
NORF	National Open Research Forum

OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RI	Research Infrastructure
RDM	Research Data Management
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA GEDE	Group of European Data Experts in RDA
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
UGOE	University of Göttingen
UEDIN	University of Edinburgh
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WG	Working Group
WDS	World Data System
WHO	World Health Organisation

Table of Contents

European Research Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technology	3
Open Geospatial Consortium	4
Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction	10
2 Achievements towards expected impact	10
2.1 Engaging research communities at early stage of standards development and address common data requirements for new services bringing together users and technology providers	10
2.2 Helping the development and adoption of relevant international open standards based on the best practices of a large spectrum of research communities	11
2.3 Enabling the use of the world’s store of research data in multi-disciplinary, data intensive global scientific collaborations	12
2.4 Enhancing the role of the Union in international organisations and multilateral fora	14
2.5 Developing cooperation with key international partners for research infrastructures	15
2.6 Promoting sustainable models for research data sharing and installing trust in the adopted solutions	16
3 RDA impact assessment: quantitative & qualitative analysis	17
3.1 Growth of the RDA community in Europe	17
3.1.1 Number of Europeans part of the RDA Governance	19
3.1.2 Number of Europeans part of the COVID groups	20
3.1.3 Membership within countries with nodes	22
3.1.4 Growth of the number of RDA European Organisational members	23
3.2 Growth of RDA awareness & adoption at national & regional level	24
3.3 Growth of RDA representation in thematic disciplines in Europe	25
3.4 Widening the RDA Early Career and Expert network in Europe	26
3.5 Wider adoption of RDA Outputs	29
3.5.1 RDA adoption grant projects	29
3.5.2 Adoption stories	30
3.5.3 RDA publications: CODATA Data Science Journal	31
3.5.4 OpenAIRE RDA Dashboard	31
3.5.5 Global collaboration on adoption of RDA outputs	31
3.6 Increasing RDA visibility and contribution to EOSC	32
3.6.1 Number of RDA members part of the EOSC Governance	32
3.6.2 EU funded projects involved in RDA	33
3.6.3 The international research data community contributing to EOSC	34
3.7 The growing RDA Social Media community	35
3.7.1 The power of national/regional networks	37
3.7.2 Educating the community via webinars	38
3.7.3 Engaging via audio-visual material	38
4 Conclusions	39

List of Tables

Table 1: Number of European members attending plenaries.....	19
Table 2: Number of Europeans part of the RDA Governance and Secretariat.....	20
Table 3: European RDA members part of the COVID-19 groups.....	22
Table 4: RDA Membership in European countries with nodes and increase during RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime.....	23
Table 6: Overview RDA Europe 4.0 Ambassador open calls.....	26
Table 7: ECR Calls and Plenaries overview.....	27
Table 8: Expert Calls and Plenaries overview.....	28
Table 9: RDA Europe 4.0 granted adoption projects.....	30
Table 10: the 38 adoption stories facilitated by RDA Europe 4.0.....	30
Table 11: Webinars organised and supported by RDA Europe 4.0.....	38
Table 12: RDA Europe 4.0 produced and promoted videos.....	38

List of Figures

Figure 1: Growth of the RDA Community in Europe.....	18
Figure 2: New RDA members since March 2020, part of COVID-19 WGs (measured August 2020).....	21
Figure 3: RDA Europe 4.0 National Node Network.....	24
Figure 4: Growth of the RDA Twitter Communities.....	35
Figure 5: P14 Day 1, Twitter campaign reactions and community engagement.....	36
Figure 6: Top performing tweets on RDA Europe 4.0 Open calls and events.....	36
Figure 7: Top performing tweet COVID-19 recommendation with attractive visual, tailor-made hashtags and tags tapping into partner's social media communities.....	37
Figure 8: RDA European newsletter recipients growth.....	37

Executive Summary

The RDA Europe 4.0 project has contributed to further expand and consolidate the European component of RDA ensuring strong links with and contribution to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). At the start of RDA Europe 4.0 there was a clear need for a better uptake of the RDA outputs and recommendations at European level. RDA Europe 4.0 contributed to this, showcasing the added value of RDA outputs for its wide variety of stakeholders through adoption stories, dedicated promotional and dissemination campaigns, the engagement of support networks (such as ambassadors, national nodes) and international and European initiatives. The RDA Europe 4.0 Cascading Grants Programme has also been instrumental to boost the European engagement in the RDA global community. The programme established fruitful and lasting network connections on EOSC, regional, domain, WG and IG levels. This will be the basis for continuation in the future in the EOSC Future proposal.

In particular, the RDA Europe 4.0 project aimed at achieving impact in six main areas defined at the time of the proposal preparation:

1. Engaging research communities at early stages of standards development and address common data requirements for new services bringing together users and technology providers
2. Helping the development and adoption of relevant international open standards based on the best practices of a large spectrum of research communities
3. Enabling the use of the world's store of research data in multi-disciplinary, data intensive global scientific collaborations
4. Enhancing the role of the Union in international organisations and multilateral fora
5. Developing cooperation with key international partners for research infrastructures
6. Promoting sustainable models for research data sharing and install trust in the adopted solutions.

Great results have been achieved in all the six areas. In particular:

Engaging research communities at early stages of standards development and address common data requirements for new services bringing together users and technology providers

The adoption of RDA outputs is one of the best indicators of the impact of RDA on the technological and societal landscape. During the RDA Europe 4.0 project, RDA has documented 142 new use-cases. Overall, 38 adoption stories were collected (of which 17 coming from the RDA Europe national nodes), published and disseminated by RDA EU 4.0; 6 adoption grants, showing cross- and multi-disciplinary implementation scenarios in European organisations have carried out adoption projects during the project lifetime. In addition, in March 2020, when the World Health Organisation (WHO) defined COVID-19 as a pandemic, the European Commission asked RDA to provide guidelines to foster COVID-19 research data sharing. The global RDA community set up a Working Group to address common data requirements for this newly defined research area rapidly bringing together users and technology providers, working on a fast track work plan, resulting in a set of adoptable guidelines and recommendations. This fast response and quick turnaround illustrated the added value of the RDA grassroot and global community and its standardised recommendations. The

RDA Europe 4.0 project supported the engagement of WG members and the promotion of the COVID-19 WG results recently presented in the EOSC Governance Symposium 2020¹.

Helping the development and adoption of relevant international open standards based on the best practices of a large spectrum of research communities

RDA fosters interoperability across regions, organisations and scientific disciplines by providing pragmatic support for transforming RDA recommendations into recognised Technical Specifications, a particular EU procedure designed to allow ICT specifications issued by a non-standards body to become endorsed standards and referenced in public procurement. During the project, the consortium has been continuously liaising with the European Commission and the Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation to increase the number of RDA recommendations transformed into ICT Technical Specifications: a third wave of four new RDA Recommendations has been submitted during the RDA Europe 4.0 project (the RDA Europe 4.0 is still awaiting the results of the assessment) and a potential fourth wave of four RDA Recommendations ready for submission to MSP has also been identified. Recognising the strategic role of standardisation for interoperability and the role of RDA in this context as a recognised and authorised organisation to submit outputs to the MSP. The activities related to the transformation of RDA outputs into ICT Technical Specifications will be continued in the recently funded INFRAEOSC03 project, EOSC Future. Starting in 2021, when the process established by RDA will be put at disposal of the full EOSC European community.

Enabling the use of the world's store of research data in multi-disciplinary, data intensive global scientific collaborations

One of the main objectives of RDA is to instill the research data sharing culture in multi-disciplinary fields. The RDA Europe 4.0 project contributed to this objective in several ways:

- Overall the RDA cascading grants mobilised over **150 individuals** active in Open Science and Research Data management in different disciplines creating opportunities for collaboration among leading edge scientists tackling issues of data interoperability.
- **33 Early Careers** have been supported by RDA Europe 4.0.
- Through its capillary network of 22 national nodes RDA Europe 4.0 ensured its impact on European organisations recruiting new early adopters but also engaging with professionals who provided fresh input and feedback to the discussions in RDA Working Groups.
- **14 Ambassadors** appointed under the umbrella of the RDA Europe programme covered active domains from Agricultural Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities to Health Sciences as well as underrepresented disciplines such as Marine Sciences with a focus on Fisheries or Engineering, and Technology with a focus on Wind Energy or Renewable Materials.
- In addition to the impact brought by the cascading grants, all the communication, engagement and adoption activities supported by the RDA Europe 4.0 project allowed to attract and onboard **8 new European RDA organisational members**.

¹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium-2020-programme>

Enhancing the role of the Union in international organisations and multilateral fora

Cooperation and coordination with other initiatives at European and global level devoted to promoting open data and interoperability was considered crucial for the uptake of the RDA principles and outputs; therefore, RDA Europe 4.0 focused on reinforcing existing and establishing new relevant collaborations and synergies. In particular, at European level, RDA Europe 4.0 has strengthened RDA's contribution to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). RDA is well represented in the EOSC governance, where four out of thirteen Executive Board members are highly involved in RDA and 45% of the EOSC WG members are also part of the RDA community. Showcasing the added value of RDA outputs and recommendations for the work of EOSC initiatives and European Strategic Research Infrastructures was also a key objective of RDA Europe 4.0: 10 adoption stories from EOSC projects and ESFRIs have been sourced, published and promoted. During the RDA Europe 4.0 project, relationships also with large multinational organizations with substantial political clout, such as GEO/GEOSS, W3C, OGC and Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) were continuously nurtured.

Developing cooperation with key international partners for research infrastructures

RDA Europe has also pursued active engagement with key partners active in the research infrastructures (RIs) landscape. The work done with the adoption projects, the national node network, the cooperation with the Group of European Data Experts in RDA (GEDE-RDA) and the European RDA members were the key factors to spread the RDA principles, outputs and best practices within the European RIs. During the RDA Europe 4.0 project's lifetime the number of RDA Working and Interest groups has increased, with the establishment of 25 new groups, as well as the number of European members that today represent 49% of the total RDA community.

Promoting sustainable models for research data sharing and install trust in the adopted solutions.

RDA Europe 4.0 has tried to foster Open Innovation by strengthening the links between research, business and education, providing connections of research with industry via the adoption grants and with education locally through the national nodes, and globally through the Ambassadors Programme.

1 Introduction

This report draws together threads from all work packages and activities within the RDA Europe 4.0 project and reflects on the impact the project has achieved. Six main areas of impact were defined for the RDA Europe 4.0 project, to which the consortium has worked towards in the past 31 months, listed here below:

- 1. It will engage research communities at early stages of standards development and address common data requirements for new services bringing together users and technology providers**
- 2. It will help the development and adoption of relevant international open standards based on the best practices of a large spectrum of research communities**
- 3. It will enable the use of the world's store of research data in multi-disciplinary, data intensive global scientific collaborations**
- 4. It will enhance the role of the Union in international organisations and multilateral fora**
- 5. It will develop cooperation with key international partners for research infrastructures**
- 6. It will promote sustainable models for research data sharing and install trust in the adopted solutions.**

In the D5.3 Interim Impact report the project partners identified the qualitative and quantitative (e.g. membership numbers, event attendance, download figures) metrics used by the project to continuously monitor and assess the impact of the project with respect to the above six areas. In this report we detail the results of the qualitative and quantitative impact assessment analysis.

2 Achievements towards expected impact

2.1 Engaging research communities at early stage of standards development and address common data requirements for new services bringing together users and technology providers

The RDA recommendations are the most tangible outputs of RDA as they support organisations and individuals in doing better science. The adoption of these outputs is one of the best indicators of the impact of RDA on the technological and societal landscape.

The RDA Europe 4.0 project worked on inspiring further uptake of RDA outputs by sharing challenges, best practices and lessons learned in the shape of adoption stories, published on the RDA website².

During the RDA Europe 4.0 project, **RDA has documented 142 new use-cases** as indicated in this list of RDA adoption use-cases³. In particular two examples were very relevant for Europe:

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-recommendations>

- FAIRsharing was adopted by 76 organisations worldwide, **at least 7 of them are European.**
- CoreTrustSeal was implemented in 100 repositories worldwide, of which **59 are European.**

Overall, 38 adoption stories were collected, published and disseminated by RDA EU 4.0 and they are reported in the *D4.3 RDA Europe contribution to RDA global* and *D5.5 Final Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Report*.

In addition, 6 adoption grants, showing cross- and multi-disciplinary implementation scenarios in European organisations have carried out adoption projects (more detail is available on these projects in *D2.3 Final RDA Results, Adoption & Take-Up report*) during the project lifetime. The adoption work and promotion of RDA was also heavily supported by the national node network that contributed with the submission and documentation of 17 adoption stories from institutions and organisations from their countries.

Furthermore, in March 2020, when the World Health Organisation (WHO) defined COVID-19 as a pandemic, the European Commission asked RDA to provide guidelines to foster COVID-19 research data sharing. The global RDA community set up a Working Group to **address common data requirements for this newly defined research area rapidly bringing together users and technology providers**, working on a fast track work plan, resulting in a set of adoptable recommendations. This fast reaction and quick turnaround illustrated the added value of the RDA grassroot and global community and its standardised guidelines and recommendations. The RDA Europe 4.0 project supported the promotion and awareness raising of the COVID-19 WG results recently presented in the EOSC Governance Symposium 2020⁴.

2.2 Helping the development and adoption of relevant international open standards based on the best practices of a large spectrum of research communities

RDA fosters interoperability across regions, organisations and scientific disciplines by providing pragmatic support for transforming RDA recommendations into recognised Technical Specifications, a particular EU procedure designed to allow ICT specifications issued by a non-standards body to become endorsed standards and referenced in public procurement. The overall ICT Technical Specifications process is overseen by the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP - E02758), an advisory expert group on ICT standardisation, to identify new RDA recommendations that could be transformed into ICT Technical Specifications.

During the project, the consortium has been continuously liaising with the European Commission and the Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation to increase the number of RDA recommendations transformed into ICT Technical Specifications.

At present, three waves of outputs (for a total of 12 outputs) from RDA Working Groups have been submitted to the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation to be recognised as ICT Technical Specifications. These were developed via the clear and transparent RDA process for producing and endorsing outputs as RDA Recommendations:

⁴ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium-2020-programme>

- **First wave: Four RDA Recommendations have been recognised as ICT technical specifications** during the RDA Europe 3.0 project. They are published in the Official Journal of the European Union “COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION (EU) 2017/1358” of 20 July 2017 on the identification of ICT Technical Specifications for referencing in public procurement <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32017D1358>. During the RDA Europe 4.0. project these four recommendations have been further promoted and their adoption increased;
- **Second wave:** Four RDA Recommendations have been recognised as ICT technical specifications during the RDA Europe 3.0 project and RDA is awaiting for their publication. RDA Europe 4.0 has liaised with the MSP to speed up their publication but the full approval process has been delayed due to the internal reorganisation of DG GROW
- **Third wave:** Four new RDA Recommendations have been submitted during the RDA Europe 4.0 project. The RDA Europe 4.0 is still awaiting the results of the assessment.
- **A potential fourth wave** of four RDA Recommendations ready for submission to MSP has also been identified during the RDA Europe 4.0 project. More information can be found in *D3.4 Final ICT Technical Specifications & contribution to standards*.

Recognising the strategic role of standardisation for interoperability and the role of RDA in this context as recognised and authorised organisation to submit outputs to the MSP. The activities related to the transformation of RDA outputs into ICT Technical Specifications will be continued in the recently funded INFRAEOSC03 project, EOSC Future. Starting in 2021 where the process established by RDA will be put at disposal of the full EOSC European community.

It should be noted that the potential impact of the ICT technical specifications activity on RDA in general and its requested contribution to EOSC in the future, is diminished as a result of the slow progress of the ICT technical specifications process. At the time of writing this report, only 4 of the 16 RDA outputs have been published in the official journal, impeding RDA from providing them with the appropriate recognition. In addition, there is potential reputational damage for the RDA in Europe and globally, in encouraging the working group, volunteer members, to provide lengthy documentation for the standardisation process, with no concrete outcome to report or demonstrate.

2.3 Enabling the use of the world’s store of research data in multi-disciplinary, data intensive global scientific collaborations

One of the main objectives of RDA is to instill the research data sharing and re-use culture in multi-disciplinary fields. The RDA Europe 4.0 project contributed to this objective in several ways via adoption, promotion and dissemination of RDA outputs etc. One above all was the work that RDA Europe 4.0 did to actively mobilize European individuals and organisations via the cascading grants mechanism that RDA Europe 4.0 piloted for the first time in the RDA history.

Overall the RDA cascading grants mobilised over **150 individuals**⁵ active in Open Science and Research Data management in different disciplines creating opportunities for collaboration among leading edge scientists tackling issues of data interoperability.

33 Early Careers from different disciplines have been supported by RDA Europe 4.0, with the aim of introducing them to the RDA and allowing them to share ideas, experiences and learn from leading scientists and researchers working in their fields or on cross-cutting data challenges. The selection process rewarded diversity and gave preference candidates from underrepresented fields that had good knowledge of the data infrastructure landscape, the European Open Science Cloud and other initiatives supporting Open Science and multidisciplinary collaboration. More information on the impact of the cascading grants for Early Careers and Experts is available in the *D2.4 'Final Impact report on support for EU participation in RDA' report*, in the process of publication at the time of writing.

With the aim to ensure wide outreach of the RDA principles of openness, community consensus and RDA's support for FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles, RDA Europe carried out a capillary campaign. At national and regional level, the project leveraged on its network of 22 national nodes. Ensuring its impact on European organisations, the project recruited new early adopters and engaged with professionals who provided fresh input and feedback to the discussions in RDA Working Groups. The national nodes have been instrumental to disseminate the RDA open calls and recruit applicants. The national nodes have also been working with national policy makers to ensure that RDA is actively involved in the regulators' and policy makers' debate, towards a global vision and lowering local legal and regulatory barriers to the free flow of data. The French Minister for Higher Education, Research and Innovation presented the National Plan for Open Science where Support the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the creation of the French Chapter of the Alliance (RDA France) is mentioned. This way RDA Europe will maximise the growth potential of the European Digital Economy. The National Nodes are supporting the shaping of the policies around Open Science in Greece, where the RDA GR node has been providing input to the Greek Open Science plan, and in Portugal, where some of the node members are working on the Open Data Strategy document.

14 Ambassadors appointed under the umbrella of the RDA Europe programme covered active domains from Agricultural Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities to Health Sciences as well as underrepresented disciplines such as Marine Sciences with a focus on Fisheries or Engineering, and Technology with a focus on Wind Energy or Renewable Materials. The Ambassador programme was created to bring representatives from different disciplinary communities into the core work of RDA, and thereby to expand both the reach of RDA's outputs within these disciplinary communities as well as the range of disciplines involved directly in the mission of the RDA. The RDA Europe 4.0 Ambassadors have actively articulated RDA's value proposition and impact for their disciplines provided resources to be leveraged by the wider community, contributed to facilitating adoption and provided valuable feedback for the processes of RDA from a disciplinary perspective. During the lifetime of the project, the ambassadors have established or leveraged an already established connection with

⁵ Number of total eligible applications received for individuals.

the RDA national nodes, helping to align disciplinary practices with national or regional approaches, creating the data-sharing synergy that is at the heart of RDA's mission.

In addition to the impact brought by the cascading grants, all the communication, engagement and adoption activities supported by the RDA Europe 4.0 project allowed to attract and onboard **8 new European RDA organisational members**:

- CESSDA, ERIC based in Norway, March 2018
- International Federation of Data Organizations (IFDO) France based, June 2018
- Digital Repository of Ireland, Ireland July 2018
- IASSIST – International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology, based in Finland, October 2018
- National Library of Ireland, Ireland, October 2018
- The Alan Turing Institute, UK, January 2019
- Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway, April 2019
- University of Strasbourg, France, December 2019

By reaching new organisational members in Europe, RDA Europe 4.0 aimed at strategically influencing RDA's direction, as organisational members are part of the RDA governance via the OAB, and thus brought an extra EU steering into the governance and assistance in the implementation and adoption of RDA's Recommendations, thus strengthening Europe's position in the emerging data economy.

2.4 Enhancing the role of the Union in international organisations and multilateral fora

Cooperation and coordination with other initiatives at European and Global level devoted to promoting open data and interoperability was considered crucial for the uptake of the RDA principles and outputs; therefore, RDA Europe 4.0 focused on reinforcing existing and establishing new relevant collaborations and synergies.

In particular, at European level, RDA Europe 4.0 has strengthened RDA's contribution to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). RDA is well represented in the EOSC governance, where four out of thirteen Executive Board members are highly involved in RDA and 45% of the EOSC WG members are also part of the RDA community. This high level of involvement and contribution was also showcased at Plenary 14 in the collocated event "The international Research Community contributing to the EOSC", where over 230 attendees discussed ongoing work, barriers and next steps towards realising the European Open Science Cloud.

Showcasing the added value of RDA outputs and recommendations for the work of EOSC initiatives and European Strategic Research Infrastructures was also a key objective of RDA Europe 4.0: **10 adoption stories from EOSC projects and ESRIs** have been sourced, published and promoted.

During the RDA Europe 4.0 project, relationships also with large multinational organizations with substantial political clout, such as AGU, COPDESS and Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) were continuously nurtured. An adoption story of

OECD has been published by RDA Europe in collaboration with RDA National Nodes⁶ and presented during the RDA Global Adoption week 2020.

The project has also continued interaction with the RDA's "sister" organizations such as ISC-CODATA and ISC-WDS. The RDA Plenary 12 has been organised in collaboration with the International Data Week, gathering over 600 participants⁷.

Collaboration has also continued with Data Seal of Approval (DSA), merged into the CoreTrustSeal. A series of 8 adoption stories - of which 5 European- has been published⁸ and presented at the RDA Global adoption week 2020⁹.

2.5 Developing cooperation with key international partners for research infrastructures

RDA Europe has also pursued active engagement with key partners active in the research infrastructures (RIs) landscape. The work done with the adoption projects, the national node network, the cooperation with the Group of European Data Experts in RDA (GEDE-RDA) and the European RDA members were the key factors to spread the RDA principles, outputs and best practices within the European RIs.

Established as part of the RDA Europe 4.0 project, the RDA national nodes in 22 European countries engaged with research communities, supported national agendas, and aimed to increase the uptake of standards and participation in RDA globally. As part of their workplans, all nodes were mandated to foster the adoption of RDA outputs in their regions. This aspect of their work included outreach to local institutions and national infrastructures to encourage the submission of adoption stories to the RDA Secretariat and articles to the CODATA Data Science Journal special collection on RDA results. This activity has resulted in 60 events and 17 adoption stories sourced by RDA nodes. Specifically two adoption stories sourced by nodes came from Research Infrastructures: *Improving Citation of evolving data in distributed asynchronous infrastructures*, an adoption story from the Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Centre (VAMDC)¹⁰, sourced by RDA France. And the *How to make FAIRness and reliability manifest: the CoreTrustSeal for TextGridRep*¹¹ adoption story from the German Chapter of the Digital Research Infrastructure from the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH-DE), sourced by RDA Germany.

The cooperation with key European partners established via the RDA adoption projects contributed to research infrastructures not only through the actual implementation of RDA outputs but also through the RDA community contributing to their implementation through development sprints and sprint sessions, user testing of new services, and presentations

⁶ <https://rd-alliance.org/towards-sustainable-research-data-repositories>

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rdas-12th-plenary-meeting-part-international-data-week-2018-gaborone-botswana>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-coretrustseal-adoption-story-across-domains-and-regions>

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-global-adoption-week-15-19-june-2020>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/improving-citation-evolving-data-distributed-asynchronous-infrastructures>

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-coretrustseal-adoption-story-across-domains-and-regions>

designed to gather attendee feedback, among others. On the other hand, the grants awarded to CCCA, BSC, and IAC allowed for projects and research infrastructures which were already established to be developed further with the implementation of RDA Recommendations and Outputs.

The Group of European Data Experts in RDA (GEDE-RDA) aims to drive consensus on guidelines, core components and concrete data fabric configuration building based on a bottom-up process. GEDE-RDA acts as a platform to engage European data professionals in a cross-disciplinary exchange of principles, recommendations and standards in the data domain. To achieve these goals GEDE-RDA is composed of a group of European data professionals appointed by invitation from various Research Infrastructures, e-Infrastructures and European co-chairs of Research Data Alliance (RDA) Groups. The RDA Europe 4.0 supported the work of the GEDE group that at the end of the project counted a total of 150 experts from more than 50 infrastructure initiatives in Europe with close interactions with GOFAIR and international groups from different countries. The list of groups involved in GEDE is an excellent indication of how large infrastructures in Europe accept RDA as a moderator to bring together data practitioners and to formulate community-driven recommendations for data sharing.

Another powerful means to bring the RDA principles, outputs and best practices to the European data practitioners and RIs was through the work done by the RDA Working and Interest Groups to which many European experts are contributing. During the RDA Europe 4.0 project's lifetime the number of RDA Working and Interest groups has increased, with the establishment of 25 new groups with a net increase of 12% of the total amount of groups (Total number of RDA WGs and IGs in March 2018: 91; Total number of RDA WGs and IGs in September 2020: 102). To maximise the impact of RDA's effort it is necessary to avoid duplication of work and guide new stakeholders across the growing landscape of RDA outputs and recommendations. RDA Europe 4.0 improved the RDA website to enhance the visibility and the browsing of the available RDA outputs to maximise adoption with the catalogue of outputs and recommendations.

As stated at the start of this paragraph, one of the key factors of the success of RDA in the European context was the contribution of its European members: the European members represent 49% of the total RDA community, all WGs and IGs have a European co-chair and all RDA governance has a balanced European representation. During the project lifetime, the European membership has seen a growth of the 36%. More quantitative information on the RDA EU members is reported in the next chapters.

2.6 Promoting sustainable models for research data sharing and installing trust in the adopted solutions

RDA Europe 4.0 has tried to foster Open Innovation by strengthening the links between research, business and education, providing connections of research with industry via the adoption grants and with education locally through the national nodes, and globally through the Ambassadors' and the Early Career Programmes.

With regards to industry, in particular BSC has worked on engaging the Earth Observation community via the Copernicus network; this was a testbed to prove how RDA can support companies building their business on creating applications and solutions on top of research

data. An adoption grant was funded with this regard.¹² In terms of education, a total of 42 webinars have been organised in the context of RDA Europe 4.0, of which 18 by the national nodes. Interesting examples are the series of webinars organised by the Italian node, gathering in around 350 participants. As well as the global adoption week 2020 gathering 33 speakers in 10 webinars spread over 5 days, engaging over 550 people all over the globe¹³. Some examples of topics covered by the webinars organised: How RDA works, [Metadata Standards Directory](#), [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools](#) in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World, [DMP Common Standards WG](#), [FAIRSharing Registry: connecting data policies, standards & databases WG](#), [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#), RDA Europe 4.0 Cascading grants.

Collaborations with industry also become visible via two adoption stories with publishers, namely Wiley on “Enabling Open Research Publishing”¹⁴ and Springer Nature on “Fostering Reproducible Research. Supporting Researchers to Publish FAIR Data Alongside Their Scholarly Publication”¹⁵. In addition, with the SME Haplo a video adoption story was recorded at IDCC2020 on “Embedding Research Data Management Plans In Ethics Approval And Funding Application Processes”¹⁶

3 RDA impact assessment: quantitative & qualitative analysis

This chapter reports the analysis of the quantitative & qualitative metrics that RDA Europe 4.0 project has continuously monitored during its duration to achieve the results documented in chapter 2.

3.1 Growth of the RDA community in Europe

The figures below show that the RDA community in Europe has grown with 36% to a total of 5272 members during the RDA Europe 4.0 project, contributing 49% of the total RDA community.

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/improving-copernicus-climate-data-store-metadata-scheme-rda-metadata-standards-repository>

¹³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-global-adoption-week-2020-insights>

¹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/enabling-open-research-publishing>

¹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/fostering-reproducible-research-supporting-researchers-publish-fair-data-alongside-their-scholarly>

¹⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/embedding-research-data-management-plans-ethics-approval-and-funding-application-processes>

Figure 1: Growth of the RDA Community in Europe

RDA Plenaries are held every six months in different places around the world. The table below shows the number of European members attending plenaries during the RDA Europe 4.0 project. Clearly the Plenaries organised in Europe are best attended by the European membership.

Country	RDA 11th Plenary Berlin, Germany	RDA 12th Plenary Gaborone, Botswana	RDA 13th Plenary Philadelphia, US	RDA 14th Plenary Helsinki, Finland	RDA 15th Plenary Melbourne, Australia
Austria	8	5	4	11	9
Belgium	14	4	4	10	1
Bulgaria		2			
Croatia				3	7
Cyprus	1				
Czech Republic	1	1		2	3
Denmark	5	1	3	6	11
Estonia	1			1	1
Finland	13	8	10	84	13
France	41	12	14	29	63
Germany	175	32	32	63	93

Greece	6		2	7	6
Hungary		1		1	5
Ireland {Republic}	4	2	4	7	14
Italy	27	9	11	19	5
Lithuania	2			1	4
Luxembourg	1				
Netherlands	40	19	22	52	48
Norway	21	1	6	21	4
Poland				1	7
Portugal	6	1	2	9	7
Romania					
Slovenia	5	1		3	9
Spain	4	1	4	8	14
Sweden	13	2	4	21	15
United Kingdom	67	40	39	67	95
Total	455	143	161	426	434
% of total attendees	69%	17%	37%	75%	39%

Table 1: Number of European members attending plenaries

3.1.1 Number of Europeans part of the RDA Governance

European representation in RDA Governance groups the Technical Advisory Board, Council and Organizational Advisory Board and Secretariat. While TAB and Council both have a maximum quote of European representation, to foster geographical balance, OAB does not have this mechanism. We can see from the table below that European members represent 50% of the total OAB, showcasing a European interest in contributing to RDA governance.

European Council members (Sep 2020)	European OAB members (Sep 2020)	European TAB members (Sep 2020)
Ingrid Dillo Co-Chair, RDA Council	OAB co-chair Kevin Ashley - Digital Curation Centre,	Isabelle Perseil - INS-RM - TAB Co-Chair

European Council members (Sep 2020)	European OAB members (Sep 2020)	European TAB members (Sep 2020)
Deputy director, Data Archiving and Networked Services	University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom)	
Sandra Collins Director, National Library of Ireland	Tuomas J. Alaterä - International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology (IASSIST)	Helen Glaves - British Geological Survey
Edit Herczog Managing Director, Vision & Values SPRL	Juan Bicarregui - Science and Technology Facilities Council (United Kingdom)	Rainer Stotzka - Steinbuch Centre for Computing, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
	Raphael Ritz - Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (Germany)	Françoise Genova - Strasbourg Astronomical Data Centre (CDS)
		Dimitris Koureas - International Biodiversity Research Infrastructures Naturalis Biodiversity Center
30% of total of 9 members	50 % of total of 8 members	30 % of total of 15 members

Table 2: Number of Europeans part of the RDA Governance and Secretariat

RDA community and governance groups endorsed 14 new Interest Groups and 11 new Working Groups have been. In this same period 9 new recommendations were endorsed (an increase of 90%) and 17 new outputs passed through community review (and increase of 340%), during the RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime.

3.1.2 Number of Europeans part of the COVID groups

As an international, consensus-driven, community-based organisation, RDA has been asked to leverage on the global RDA data community to support the urgent Coronavirus COVID-19 pandemic. As a response, RDA has set up the fast track COVID-19 Working Group to define detailed guidelines on data sharing and re-use under the present COVID-19 circumstances to help researchers follow best practices to maximize the efficiency of their work. The guidelines focus on the management of data originating from different data sources and the development of a system for data sharing in public health emergencies that supports scientific research.

Since March up to September 2020, 322 new users from Europe joined RDA and the RDA COVID19 WG, out of the 505 overall unique members spread all over the seven sub-groups (data up to September 2020), demonstrating a great interest and engagement from the European community to the Group cause.

RDA EU - New users since March 2020 part of COVID-19 WGs

Last update: 18 June 2020

Figure 2: New RDA members since March 2020, part of COVID-19 WGs (measured August 2020)

Country	European RDA Members part of COVID groups
Austria	7
Belgium	18
Bulgaria	2
Czech Republic	3
Denmark	4
Finland	4

Country	European RDA Members part of COVID groups
France	60
Germany	50
Greece	12
Ireland {Republic}	11
Italy	26
Lithuania	1
Luxembourg	4
Netherlands	22
Poland	1
Portugal	7
Romania	6
Slovenia	1
Spain	19
Sweden	6
United Kingdom	58
Total	322

Table 3: European RDA members part of the COVID-19 groups

3.1.3 Membership within countries with nodes

The RDA Europe 4.0 national nodes heavily contributed to the growth of the European RDA community.

Country	RDA Members (Node start date)	RDA Members (Sept. 2020)	Increase
Austria	65	107	65%
Bulgaria	9	27	200%
Croatia	26	52	100%
Czech Republic	33	40	21%
Denmark	62	117	89%
Estonia	19	25	32%
Finland	146	257	76%

Country	RDA Members (Node start date)	RDA Members (Sept. 2020)	Increase
France	332	663	100%
Germany	494	735	49%
Greece	112	167	49%
Hungary	50	58	16%
Ireland {Republic}	138	187	36%
Italy	304	447	47%
Lithuania	17	23	35%
Netherlands	289	424	47%
Norway	102	167	64%
Portugal	57	219	284%
Romania	26	128	392%
Slovenia	13	57	338%
Spain	276	372	35%
Sweden	82	122	49%
United Kingdom	683	944	38%

Table 4: RDA Membership in European countries with nodes and increase during RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime

3.1.4 Growth of the number of RDA European Organisational members

8 new European RDA organisational members joined RDA during the duration of the RDA Europe 4.0 project:

1. CESSDA, ERIC based in Norway, March 2018
2. International Federation of Data Organizations (IFDO) France based, June 2018
3. Digital Repository of Ireland, Ireland July 2018
4. IASS–ST - International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology, based in Finland, October 2018
5. National Library of Ireland, Ireland, October 2018
6. The Alan Turing Institute, UK, January 2019
7. Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway, April 2019
8. University of Strasbourg, France, December 2019

27 out of the 62 current Organisation and Affiliate members come from Europe (43%)¹⁷

¹⁷ See the OA and OAB catalogue <https://www.rd-alliance.org/oa-members>

3.2 Growth of RDA awareness & adoption at national & regional level

The National Nodes community grew over the duration of RDA Europe 4.0 thanks to the cascading grants mechanism. In addition to the nine pioneer Nodes that started working on their national communities and priorities at the very beginning of the project, thirteen more were selected in three different waves of open calls.

Figure 3: RDA Europe 4.0 National Node Network

The fact the selected institutions were relevant players in their countries regarding Open Science, contributed to attract new members to RDA and to influence the national policy agendas.

In fact, the National Nodes had a specific section in their workplans about the engagement with relevant stakeholders, in particular national research funding bodies. All of them ensured to

organise periodical meetings with the major funding bodies and research ministries, not only to disseminate RDA results but also to ensure wide awareness of ongoing policies around open science and data management. Some of the National Nodes achieved very positive results out of this engagement activity. To give some examples, the French Minister for Higher Education, Research and Innovation presented the National Plan for Open Science where support the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the creation of a French Chapter of the Alliance (RDA France) is mentioned. Other National Nodes are supporting the shaping of the policies around Open Science, i.e. in Greece, where the RDA GR node has been providing input to the Greek Open Science plan, and in Portugal, where some of the node members are working on the Open Data Strategy document. In Ireland, the National Node will be active in the working groups of the National Open Research Forum (NORF). Moreover, the Italian Node will be involved in the national EOSC Competence Centre thanks to the previous engagement with the Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (ICDI).

The national nodes also helped strengthening the connections with EU-funded and EOSC-related projects and RDA.

Among the other tasks they also disseminated the RDA outputs and facilitated their adoption: 16 adoption stories are documented by the end of the project.

3.3 Growth of RDA representation in thematic disciplines in Europe

The engagement of disciplinary communities has been one of the priorities of the RDA EU Ambassadors programme, running from March 2018 until September 2020. The Ambassador programme was created to bring representatives from different disciplinary communities into the core work of RDA, and thereby expand both the reach of RDA's outputs within these disciplinary communities as well as the range of disciplines involved directly in the mission of the RDA. **The 14 Ambassadors appointed under the umbrella of the RDA Europe programme covered active domains from Agricultural Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities to Health Sciences as well as underrepresented disciplines such as Marine Sciences with a focus on Fisheries or Engineering, and Technology with a focus on Wind Energy or Renewable Materials.**

The RDA Europe 4.0 project organised two open call waves for the recruitment of 12 Ambassadors in addition to the two Ambassadors, for Social Sciences and the Humanities supported by the NL national node coordinator, DANS as part of the expert commitment to the RDA EU 4.0 project..

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
1st wave	17	6	5 Denmark, France, Italy, Slovenia, United Kingdom	2 Female / 4 Male

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
2nd wave	10	6	6 United Kingdom, Netherlands, Germany, Spain, Greece, France	4 Female / 2 Male
Ambassadors supported by nodes*	-	2	1 Netherlands	1 Female / 1 Male

Table 5: Overview RDA Europe 4.0 Ambassador open calls

The RDA Europe 4.0 Ambassadors have actively articulated RDA’s value proposition and impact for their disciplines provided resources to be leveraged by the wider community, contributed to facilitating adoption and provided valuable feedback for the processes of RDA from a disciplinary perspective. For example, Dr. Ricarda Braukmann - RDA EU Ambassador for Social Sciences published a report that categorises and details the specific benefits of RDA to the Social Sciences. Over the duration of the project the report has been updated and the latest version with the supporting data openly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1401104>. This report combined with the Ambassador’s other outreach efforts are cited in the case statement of the newly created Interest Group on Humanities and Social Sciences¹⁸. A similar output was provided by Rene van Horik, RDA EU Ambassador for Humanities. His report [RDA for the Humanities](#) also covers synergies with initiative such CLARIN or DARIAH.

Similar overviews to identify, delineate, and map RDA working groups and outputs were provided under the discipline pages with Ambassadors either authoring the complete overview e.g. [RDA and Scholarly Communication](#) or contributing to already existing pages e.g. [RDA and Digital Humanities](#). Nikola Vasiljevic (RDA EU Ambassador for Engineering and Technology / Wind energy) provided an alternative analysis but adopted a different approach for his “The assessment of RDA through the prism of wind energy community”, hosted on Github as a live document: <https://github.com/niva83/RDA-assessment>

During the lifetime of the project, the Ambassadors have established or leveraged an already established connection with the RDA national nodes, helping to align disciplinary practices with national or regional approaches, creating the data-sharing synergy that is at the heart of RDA’s mission.

3.4 Widening the RDA Early Career and Expert network in Europe

Both the Early Career and Expert grants programmes were designed to support individual participation in the RDA. These programmes offered grant winners the opportunity to engage directly with and support the work of the RDA Working and Interest Groups, contribute and become a part of the RDA global data sharing community.

¹⁸ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/social-sciences-humanities-research-data-ig>

The programmes were aligned with both the European project objectives of supporting European participation and contribution to RDA and the RDA global vision of engaging a diversified and inter-generational community.

A total of 75 eligible applications for the Early Career grants were received and 33 grantees were selected. The table below illustrates the figures in relation to each Plenary and Open Call process.

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
11 th Plenary, March 2018, Berlin	2	1	1 United Kingdom	1 Female
12 th Plenary, Nov 2018, Botswana	17	8	6 Slovenia, Germany, Netherlands, Italy, Austria, Portugal	6 Female / 2 Male
13 th Plenary, April 2019, Philadelphia	19	7	7 Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, France, Austria, Germany, Portugal	4 Female / 3 Male
14 th Plenary, October 2019, Helsinki	21	10	8 Hungary, Portugal, Austria, Spain, Greece, Germany, Netherlands, United Kingdom	5 Female / 5 Male
15 th Plenary, March 2020	16	7	5 Germany, Hungary, Croatia, Romania (initial selection also included Estonia)	5 Female / 2 Male

Table 6: ECR Calls and Plenaries overview

A total of 63 eligible applications were received for the Expert grants and 28 grantees were selected. The table below illustrates the figures in relation to each Plenary and Open Call process.

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
11 th Plenary	11	5	4 Austria, Spain, Greece, Finland	2 Female / 3 Male
12 th Plenary	12	5	2 United Kingdom, Austria	1 Female / 4 Male

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
13 th Plenary	10	6	5 United Kingdom, Greece, France, Ireland, Italy	2 Female / 4 Male
14 th Plenary	14	7	6 Germany, Spain, Greece, Sweden, Netherlands, United Kingdom	4 Female / 3 Male
15 th Plenary	16	5	5 Finland, Italy, Denmark, Ireland, Germany (initial selection also included Hungary ¹⁹)	2 Female / 4 Male

Table 7: Expert Calls and Plenaries overview

The two grant programmes complemented each other in the effort to foster inter-generational exchange between researchers at different career levels. Case in point, Early Career grantees have been assigned to and encouraged to join the Early Career and Engagement IG and leverage their Mentorship programme to which Expert grantees have signed up as mentors. The initiative brings together senior RDA members and researchers at the beginning of their career and newcomers to RDA. This helped to bring different generations into the RDA, which contributes to the diversity of ideas, and to RDA's sustainability.

There are several examples of how the Early Career grant program has made a notable impact on the careers of winners, which in turn has benefited the growth of RDA and its impact. For example, several grantees have become chairs of RDA WGs or IGs or have taken on active roles in various groups:

- João Rocha became chair of the Repository Platforms for Research Data IG, has suggested setting up a WG (driven by the RPRD IG) as a forum for discussion and comparison of research data management platforms
- Kathleen Gregory has been actively involved with the Data Discovery Paradigms IG, she is co-author on the best practices article published as an output from the IG
- Daniela Hausen has contributed to the Research data management in Engineering IG charter
- Romain David provided presentations at both SHARing Rewards & Credit IG and Agrisemantics WG meetings during the 13th RDA Plenary - both group activities are connected to his work at INRA and PhD project.

The impact of this is clear: early-career researchers, given the opportunity to attend RDA plenaries and be actively introduced to WGs/IGs through the conditions of their grant, then

¹⁹ Due to the COVID-19 situation and travel restrictions, a number of candidates from the initially selected cohort withdrew. The Grants Committee proceeded in contacting the candidates based on their evaluation ranking to fill in the grant slots available.

gain experience and become influencers in their domain (not to mention, they help to grow their communities).

With regards to the experts, the input collected through their reports was taken up as critical feedback on the work of RDA by triggering the set-up of a taskforce to look at more in detail into operational and organisational aspects of RDA related to quality checks, duration of various steps and processes set out for the group activities.

3.5 Wider adoption of RDA Outputs

26 RDA outputs and recommendations have been produced during the RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime. RDA Europe 4.0 has contributed to increasing their visibility to inspire wider adoption. Via the Adoption Stories and promotion via its cascading grants programme, particularly the Node network, the ambassadors and the adoption projects. As well we via the CODATA Data Science Journal special collection on RDA and the global collaboration on adoption of RDA outputs (see *D4.3 RDA Europe contribution to RDA global*).

3.5.1 RDA adoption grant projects

Following an Adoption Open Call in 2019, the RDA Europe 4.0 project initially funded eight organisations to adopt one or more existing RDA recommendations and/or outputs. These adoption grant projects were intended to provide a valuable testbed for the adoption of a range of RDA Recommendations and Outputs and to disseminate their projects to as wide an audience as possible as adoption use cases.

Thirteen applications for these grants were received from nine different countries. A strong range of proposals were put forward, covering a variety of outputs and disciplines. Eight applications were funded of which finally six projects were carried out as explained in D2.3.

Project title	Organisation, Country	Recommendation(s)/Output(s) adopted
23 Things Revisited: Field guides to research data management	SURFSara, Netherlands	23 Things: Libraries For Research Data
A Road to a Hungarian Data Publishing Policy	University of Debrecen and Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Hungary	Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components Repository Audit and Certification Catalogues
CCCA Subset & Dynamic Data Citation Service	Climate Change Centre Austria, Austria	Scalable Dynamic-data Citation Methodology
Improving the Copernicus Climate Data Store metadata scheme with the “RDA metadata standards repository”	Barcelona Supercomputing Centre, Spain	Metadata Standards Directory

Project title	Organisation, Country	Recommendation(s)/Output(s) adopted
Template for reproducible, shareable and achievable data analysis	Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, Spain	Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components
A model of data integration related to wheat genetic resources and resistance to Fusarium head blight	Sofia University Saint Kliment Ohridski, Bulgaria	Wheat Data Interoperability Guidelines, Ontologies and User Cases

Table 8: RDA Europe 4.0 granted adoption projects

3.5.2 Adoption stories

As described in *D4.3* a total of **38 adoption stories** were published at <https://www.rda-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories> during the RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime. Stories were widely disseminated via the RDA channels and viewed **12.200+ times**. These adoption stories served as a basis to highlight the RDA Outputs and Recommendations in RDA European Node events and RDA ambassador presentations. During the RDA plenary meetings from P12-P15 Adoption and Outputs sessions **58 highlights** were given to **individual RDA outputs & recommendations** (see *D2.3 “Final RDA Results, Adoption & Take up report”*).

Adoption story categories	number of stories in category
European Adoption stories	Of the total of 38 stories, 30 are European
EOSC & ESFRI related adoption stories	Of the total of 38 stories, 10 stories come from the EOSC & ESFRI ecosystem.
Adoption stories facilitated by nodes	Of the total of 38 stories, 17 stories are facilitated by the nodes.
Stories by adoption projects	Of the total of 38 stories, 6 stories are facilitated by the adoption projects.
Adoption story by ambassador	Of the total of 38 stories, 1 story is facilitated by an RDA ambassador.
Adoption stories on recently endorsed outputs & recommendations ²⁰	Of the total of 38 stories, 25 stories highlight the adoption of recently published outputs & recommendations.

Table 9: the 38 adoption stories facilitated by RDA Europe 4.0

²⁰ This includes the 8 stories coming from the CoreTrustSeal adoption case. The RDA Recommendation Repository Audit and Certification Catalogues was endorsed before the RDA Europe project started, while the CoreTrustSeal Foundation Statutes and Rules of Procedure entered into force in February 2018 <https://zenodo.org/record/1142960#.X4gizFIS9TZ>. Read the story behind the certification process here <https://www.coretrustseal.org/about/history/>

3.5.3 RDA publications: CODATA Data Science Journal

The CODATA Data Science Journal special collection²¹ gathers and promotes research results and outcomes stemming from the Research Data Alliance activities. In particular, it collects high quality papers describing the latest results of RDA working groups (WGs) or interest groups (IGs) focusing particularly on use cases that highlight the added value of the RDA solutions for different challenges related to research data sharing and management.

The scope of this special collection is to ultimately become a point of reference for experts from the international community that are committed to enabling data sharing, exchange, and interoperability by showcasing the various RDA results and how these have been implemented across disciplines, organisations and geographies. RDA Europe 4.0 funded the Article Processing Costs (APCs) of 9 peer reviewed and published articles and an additional 19 submitted papers, currently in review. The full list of papers published up to July 2020 can be consulted in D2.3 Final RDA results adoption and take-up report.

Up to September 2020, the 9 published papers have been viewed **11227 times**, **downloaded 2316 times**, **cited 8 times** and **tweeted about 641 times**. Due to this impact and the aim of the collection to serve as a reference point for the international community committed to establishing open data sharing, the Data Science Journal Research Data Alliance special collection editors have indicated the collection will remain open. Allowing additional RDA results to be added to the reference collection for data sharing, such as papers on the recently published recommendations from the COVID-19 Working Group.

3.5.4 OpenAIRE RDA Dashboard

In collaboration with OpenAIRE, RDA set up a Research Community Dashboard dedicated to showcase the results of the RDA community at large. Although not public yet, the dashboard will be accessible at <https://beta.rda.openaire.eu/>. The dashboard collects the research outputs related to RDA, from publications to research data to software, by linking the two communities RDA maintains on Zenodo (one contains the RDA official documents, including the recommendations and outputs; the other is about all documents related to RDA, e.g. journal articles, project deliverables etc.); moreover, through a text and data mining mechanism, the dashboard analyses the metadata and full-texts of the OpenAIRE Research Graph searching for RDA-related outputs matching the defined mining rules. Ideally, the RDA community at large will take ownership of the dashboard and maintain it in the long-term with the technical support from OpenAIRE. In addition to the dashboard, OpenAIRE provides RDA with an overview of the results linked to the RDA Europe 4.0 via the Explore portal;²² that shows quite some interaction with the project outputs, i.e. 5,532 downloads and 8,814 total views.

3.5.5 Global collaboration on adoption of RDA outputs

As reported in D2.3 and D4.4 the Secretariat Adoption task force works on fostering adoption of the RDA Outputs & Recommendation through enhanced discoverability and intelligibility

²¹ CODATA Data Science Journal special collection:

<https://datascience.codata.org/collections/special/research-data-alliance-results/>

²² https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::40ac835c7ff2b6f244f88467221aa88d

of RDA recommendations, outputs, and adoption stories, Adoption support through education material development and monitoring and evaluation of adoption impact.

During the RDA Europe lifetime we see an increased visibility of the 49 available RDA Outputs and Recommendations has increased with 810% of ZENODO views (with 6K+) and 807% of ZENODO downloads (with 11K+) from July 2019 to September 2020. In addition, the RDA Outputs and Recommendations have received 180% more reads in September 2020 in comparison with July 2019 (320K reads).

In the RDA nutshell of March 2018 75 use cases were reported, at the time of writing September 2020, this number has risen to 142 use-cases²³, plus a direct link to the CoreTrustSeal interactive map where all additional 90+ certified repositories can be consulted. This shows an increase of 317% of documented adoption cases.

Outside of the funded adoption projects themselves, the adoption and uptake of RDA Recommendations and Outputs has been supported by the activities of the other areas which received RDA Europe 4.0 funding; the RDA National Node network has supported the adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs and has had a hand in the production of a number of Adoption Stories, while the RDA Europe Ambassadors have been directly involved in cases of adoption and have collaborated on further Adoption Stories, as listed in D2.³²⁴

3.6 Increasing RDA visibility and contribution to EOSC

3.6.1 Number of RDA members part of the EOSC Governance

EOSC is an emerging European federated data commons for Open Science in Europe. RDA and its international research community contribute to the implementation phase of the EOSC through its involvement in EOSC governance and working groups. The tables below show the involvement of RDA Europe in the EOSC governance and Working Groups.

RDA Member	RDA involvement	EOSC governance
Sarah Jones	RDA Europe 4.0	EOSC FAIR WG chair
Juan Bicarregui	RDA UK Node	Rules of Participation (RoP) WG Chair, RDA representative in EOSC
Ron Dekker	RDA IG chair	EOSC EB
Kathleen Shearer	RDA IG chair	EOSC EB

EOSC WG	No of RDA members	% of group
Architecture	22	43%
FAIR	22	73%

²³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-recommendations>

²⁴ D2.3 Final RDA results, Adoption & Uptake report.

EOSC WG	No of RDA members	% of group
Rules of Participation	8	34%
Landscape	11	35%
Sustainability	8	30%
Training & Skills	23	55%

3.6.2 EU funded projects involved in RDA

In the framework of the project, RDA Europe 4.0 surveyed 30 EOSC-related H2020 projects (funded by DG RTD and DG CNECT) to identify the specific inputs and benefits that RDA brings to EOSC-related projects in terms of tangible guidelines (in the form of RDA Recommendations and Outputs) and in terms of network and community building. RDA awareness among EOSC projects is high, with involvement ranging from membership and adoption to plans for more formalised collaboration. Most projects are engaged with RDA through individual membership, attendance at plenaries, or presentation of project outcomes at RDA events. Some EOSC projects include targeted tasks in their workplans involving practical collaboration with RDA. RDA is one of the preferred channels for EOSC-related projects to build their international network of researchers and data practitioners.

Under Task 3.4 a **series of collaborations have been established with a set of EOSC-related projects**: EOSC-hub, OpenAIRE, FREYA, FAIRsFAIR and EOSC Secretariat. In particular, the collaboration with EOSC-hub and OpenAIRE has been focused on investigating synergies at national level to understand how these initiatives can support Open Science national agendas; FAIR was also one of the most important themes at the basis of the collaboration, including

also the Horizon 2020-funded FAIRsFAIR project. A series of workshops has been run to discuss services to make data FAIR offered by the different initiatives and related gaps. The results of the follow up workshop on FAIR, that took place in September 2019 at the Open Science Fair addressing more the analysis of the FAIR landscape, fed the EOSC FAIR Working Group. **The outcomes of these workshops are summarised in a news item on the RDA website²⁵ and in an article published in Patterns journal²⁶.**

Collaborations with the EOSC cluster projects. The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project led to a series of two articles by SSHOC, inspired on the RDA ambassador report for the social sciences²⁷. The articles showcase how the RDA impacts social sciences research, where the first article shows us what's in it for SSHOC²⁸, the second article provides feedback from SSHOC Project Partners²⁹. During the P14 a collocated event was organised by SSHOC on EOSC. ESFRI Cluster Projects. RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services involving CLARIN, CESSDA, ESCAPE, ENVRI-FAIR, PANOSC and RDA WG/IGs and RDA GEDE. A report was published here: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3581075. SSHOC has provided 2 adoption stories *The Ethnic And Migrant Minorities' (EMMs') Survey Registry: A Tool To Help Make EMM Survey Data FAIR*³⁰ and *An agreed approach to assessing the trustworthiness and quality of SSH data repositories in EOSC*³¹ on the adoption plan of SSHOC of the CoreTrustSeal certification across ten Social Sciences and Humanities repositories³². Both SSHOC project partners CLARIN and CESSDA presented this plan during the global adoption week 2020.

In *D3.3 Report on RDA integration with other European initiatives* each National Node reported details on the national framework and specifically on the relationship and involvement with any EU funded projects. Notably, all the nodes have established some kind of interactions with key EU and EOSC-related projects, either because the institution representing the national node sits in the project consortium or because of the importance of the very same institution in the national landscape.

3.6.3 The international research data community contributing to EOSC

To further consolidate the role of RDA as the place where to meet the international research data community, the EOSC Executive Board reached out to the RDA Europe 4.0 project to organise an **EOSC workshop in conjunction with the Helsinki Plenary 14 of RDA**³³. The event took place the day before the Helsinki Plenary started. With 230 participants it

²⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-services-fair-data-ecosystem-0>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2020.100058>

²⁷ <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3580674>

²⁸ <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/how-rda-impacts-social-sciences-research-and-what's-it-sshoc>

²⁹ <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/how-rda-impacts-sshoc-feedback-project-partners>

³⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/ethnic-and-migrant-minorities-emms-survey-registry-tool-help-make-emm-survey-data-fair>

³¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-coretrustseal-adoption-story-across-domains-and-regions>

³² <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/d82-certification-plan-sshoc-repositories>

³³ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/international-research-data-community-contributing-eosc>

provided a voice to the research data community of stakeholders in a global setting on the European Open Science Cloud progress and early results, covering topics around the EOSC Governance Vision and Roadmap, as well as updates from the five EOSC Working Groups. Moreover, taking advantage of the international dimension of the event, representatives from the Governance Board offered their national perspectives and agendas around research data to collect feedback and share lessons learned with representatives from other regions.

3.7 The growing RDA Social Media community

During the project, the community engagement as represented on RDA social media grew significantly with a total of 11,624 Twitter followers, 4,283 connections and 417 contacts on LinkedIn, and 96 YouTube followers, adding up to a total of 16,396 RDA connections. The RDA Europe Twitter social media community grew with 71.7 %, the RDA global community with over 60.7% over the period of M1-M31.

Figure 4: Growth of the RDA Twitter Communities

To briefly showcase the engagement of the RDA community in response to the communication activities outlined so far in this document on the growth of RDA Global, Twitter metrics will be shown to illustrate the impact of community engagement activity with RDA around the launch of RDA Europe 4.0 and RDA P14 in Helsinki (23-25 October 2019).

As with all plenaries, in preparation for the event in the months leading up to P14, RDA’s communication activities were focused around the promotion of important deadlines around calls for sessions and posters, the publication of the programme, speaker profiles, etc. The figure below shows an increase in activity and community response to the marketing campaigns from 14/10/2019 onwards in the weeks leading up to the Helsinki plenary.

Figure 5: P14 Day 1, Twitter campaign reactions and community engagement

In *D4.4 RDA Europe Global Communication Strategy* we compared the increased engagement of the RDA community around plenaries P9 and P14, both in Europe. Only 2,5 years later the engagement nearly tripled, with over 36,000 organic impressions on the first day of RDA P14 in Helsinki in October 2019. The RDA community as seen on social media has grown, and in response to the communication campaigns, their engagement has increased.

Top performing tweets

Messages on RDA outputs, RDA EU 4.0 calls and the node network have gained a lot of visibility.

Are you an **#OpenScience #Researcher** interested in Training **#FAIRdata** & Certification? Join the **@RDA_Europe UK** & **@OpenAIRE_eu** Virtual Workshop to connect with other **#researchers** & **#policy** makers with a strong focus on **#FAIR**. Learn more: rd-alliance.org/group/rda-unit..

Building bridges across Open Science in the UK
6 May 2020 - 13:30 UTC

4:43 PM · Apr 23, 2020 · PostPickr

17 Retweets 20 Likes

Will you be one of the nine **Early Career Researchers** that will get support from **@RDA_Europe** to attend the 14th **#RDAPlenary** in **#Helsinki**, Finland, from 23-25 October 2019? Hurry up and apply for our grants by August 16! grants.rd-alliance.org/OpenCalls/call..

11:50 AM · Jul 12, 2019 · Hootsuite Inc.

21 Retweets 2 Quote Tweets 14 Likes

Figure 6: Top performing tweets on RDA Europe 4.0 Open calls and events

The figure below shows the example of a Tweet that has achieved 4712 impressions, 14 click on the link, 11 retweets and 4 profile clicks, thanks to a catchy visual, a tailor-made use of hashtags, that are an integral part of the text itself, and the use of tags to tap into the partners' social media communities.

Figure 7: Top performing tweet COVID-19 recommendation with attractive visual, tailor-made hashtags and tags tapping into partner's social media communities.

3.7.1 The power of national/regional networks

Fourteen dedicated Node newsletters have been sent to a growing community of European RDA members that reached up to 6239 recipients in June 2020. In addition, some announcements were also sent to specific national groups as an additional support given the Nodes in their initial phase of community growing and in addition to the activities they have been undergoing within their National Group pages.

Figure 8: RDA European newsletter recipients growth

3.7.2 Educating the community via webinars

As reported in *D5.5 Final Communication, Marketing & Stakeholders Engagement report* RDA Europe 4.0 organised and promoted a total of 42 webinars, of which recordings and slide decks have been made available and accessible for the RDA communities.

Webinar type	Number
RDA Europe 4.0 webinars	6
RDA nodes webinars	18
RDA adoption webinars	12
RDA Ambassador webinar	2
RDA GEDE webinars	4

Table 10: Webinars organised and supported by RDA Europe 4.0

3.7.3 Engaging via audio-visual material

RDA Europe has delivered and promoted 48 videos promoting the RDA Plenaries, Adoption of outputs and recommendations, the European node network and ambassadors. The table below provides an overview of the videos produced and made available for reuse and their impact measured by amount of views.

Video	Aim	Impact by number of views
RDA in-one-word https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BdD2NTytb8Q	Interviews at P13 to increase visibility of RDA and the community.	362
Adopting RDA outputs https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dvv530p6VBU	Raise awareness on adoption of RDA outputs and the call for adoption stories	200
P14 promotion https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FsvOOfxDXQE	Promote RDA P14 in Helsinki	233
21 RDA Node videos	Promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes video.	1705
4 RDA ambassador videos	Promotion of RDA Europe ambassadors and their roles in RDA Europe 4.0 and the global community.	189
20 RDA adoption videos	Promotion of RDA Europe Adoption Stories: Description of the Adopted Output, Challenges of the Adoption and Impact of the Adoption.	529

Table 11: RDA Europe 4.0 produced and promoted videos

4 Conclusions

RDA is an enabling organisation offering a global, open, neutral, community-driven, and independent forum serving multiple stakeholders and covering all scientific disciplines and research domains. There are numerous examples of domain-specific and multi-disciplinary communities that do this, but RDA is one of the few, if not the only one, that places the individual at the heart and therefore has succeeded in occupying this role in the RDM ecosystem. Furthermore, RDA enables the cross fertilisation of best practices, knowledge and solutions across different communities and makes all its outputs open and available to all.

The RDA community in Europe has consolidated over the lifetime of the RDA Europe 4.0 project while at the same time a steady growth in European contributions to and engagement with RDA on a global level are clearly evidenced in this report.

European support for RDA benefits all European stakeholders in ensuring that community-based solutions to data challenges are developed and adopted globally, supporting the interoperability and FAIR challenges.

At the start of RDA Europe 4.0 there was a clear need for a better uptake of the RDA outputs and recommendations at European level. RDA Europe 4.0 contributed to this by showcasing the added value of RDA outputs for its wide variety of stakeholders through adoption stories, dedicated promotional and dissemination campaigns, the engagement of support networks (such as ambassadors, national nodes) and international and European initiatives.

The RDA Europe 4.0 Cascading grants programme has also been instrumental to boost the European engagement in the RDA global community. The programme established fruitful and lasting network connections on EOSC, regional, domain, WG and IG levels. This will be the basis for continuation in the coming years in the EOSC Future proposal.